

Quantum Mechanics, Photons and No Rest Frame or Rest Co-ordinate Axes?

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. May 13, 2025

In previous notes, we argued that $x=ct$ (initial conditions $x=0, t=0$) as well as $E=pc$ for a photon and so made the association: $\text{constant}/p = \lambda$ (wavelength) and $\text{constant}/E = \text{period}$. We then argued that these designations should carry over to a particle with rest mass even though its speed is not c , hence giving rise to free particle quantum mechanics.

Here, we wish to examine and clarify these ideas in order to hopefully strengthen the association of E and p with period and wavelength, which may at first appear arbitrary or coincidental. In particular, we make use of the idea that even though rest mass, m_0 , defines a rest frame, which in turn is used to define motion (relative to rest) of such a particle, the parameter c arises in the derivation of a Lorentz transformation strictly for a particle with rest mass. We argue that this may imply that some photonic features are present in such a particle. In addition, we argue that $E=pc$, which follows from $E^2 = p^2c^2 + m_0^2c^4$ is related to the idea of no rest frame (or rest mass) for a photon. We suggest that this actually implies that one should not consider an $(x-t)$ co-ordinate system being associated with the photon. We have argued that a measurement co-ordinate system is like having a rest frame and this does not apply to a photon. Thus, $x=ct$ and $E=pc$ may be considered to be one and the same equation in that: $\text{wavelength}=\text{constant}/p$ and $\text{period} = \text{constant}/E$ as there is no rest frame $x-t$ system for a photon. (That is not to say that it cannot be measured in a frame linked with other rest objects, but it always has the same speed in any of these frames.) As a result, associating E and p with period and wavelength for a photon does not seem to be arbitrary, but is based on the lack of rest frame. We give arguments for extending these wavelength and period ideas to a particle with rest mass based on experimental independence of E and p measurements and degeneracies, such as $p=m_1v_1=m_2v_2$ etc. Thus, even though v for such a particle is measured relative to a rest frame and p and E are based on m_0 , a given p is not linked to any particular m_0 value and $v_1=x'/t', v_2=x''/t''$ etc are different frames suggesting that it may be good to have an intrinsic set of co-ordinate units defined by period and wavelength.

Derivation of the Lorentz Transformation for a Particle with Rest Mass

We have derived the Lorentz transformation for a particle with rest mass in various previous notes. Here we suggest that the rest mass is key to defining the rest frame, but so is the co-ordinate axes in this frame. Furthermore, rest mass is key in the definitions of energy and momentum. We also note that given a rest frame, a moving frame ($-v$) is defined based on the rest frame and so motion of the particle itself seems to be linked to a rest frame which is guaranteed to exist. In such a scheme, it seems that there would be no link whatsoever with a photon which is very different. The problem is that in writing a transformation and creating an x,t vector, the transformation must have dimensionless numbers and x and t must have the same units, so:

tb is a vector component, where b is the same in all frames and has speed units ((1))

Given $x=0$, t in the rest frame and $x'/t' = v$ in the moving (motion defined relative to the rest frame) that:

$$x' = g(v) v t \quad \text{and} \quad t' = g(v) t \quad ((2))$$

Furthermore, enforcing: $xx - b^2tt = x'x' - b^2t't'$ leads to: $g(v) = 1/\sqrt{1-vv/bb}$ ((3))

As a result, it is not sufficient to have one speed in the picture, v , but there exists a second which is the same in all frames, namely b . We ask two questions. First, what is b ? Second, what does it have to do with a particle with rest mass?

If one applies the Lorentz transform to m_0 and $p=0$, then:

$$E'E = p'p' bb + m_0 m_0 bbb \quad ((4))$$

For $m_0=0$, one has: $E' = p' b$ ((5))

For $m_0=0$, there is no rest frame and we argue that there should also be no intrinsic $x-t$ co-ordinate system because this implies a rest frame. In other words,

$$E' = p' b \quad \text{and} \quad x' = b t' \quad \text{should be one and the same equation} \quad ((6))$$

It is not simply a coincidence that the two have the same form and we argue that one is not being arbitrary in assigning:

$$\text{constant}/E' = \text{period} \quad \text{and} \quad \text{constant}/p' = \text{wavelength} \quad ((7))$$

This leads to: $b = \text{frequency} * \text{wavelength}$ which is the equation for a wave, which does not have a rest mass. We suggest that the object in ((5)), ((7)) is a photon and that its E and p really define time and space for it because there is no rest frame to hold a co-ordinate system ($x-t$). One may argue that this is fine, but what is the connection with a particle with rest mass, if any?

We try to argue that if there is no connection between a particle with rest mass and a photon, then there should be no $b=c$ appearing in the Lorentz transformation or the vector, (x, bt) . In other words, if $b=c$ is simply an upper bound on v , then frequency and wavelength features should not turn on only upon reaching this limit, it seems. (We have made this argument in previous notes.)

Certainly, motion for a particle with rest mass is defined by v , the speed of the moving frame relative to the rest frame. One does not have ((6)) as for a photon. Nevertheless, a photon has the feature that there is a built-in $x-t$ co-ordinate system, linked with 2-slit interference, in the photon. This is a physical feature and is based on E and p . On the one hand, both a particle with rest mass and a photon have energy and momentum which is measured in a similar manner. For example, momentum may be measured for both by a collision with a target. The issue is that for a particle with a rest mass, the energy and momentum are proportional to m_0

which is linked directly to a rest frame. We have noted before, however, that a target measurement of p is the same for:

$$p=m_1v_1=m_2v_2=m_3v_3 \dots \quad ((8))$$

The actual value of rest mass is not key for momentum. One might argue that a photon with p strikes a target with a certain impact and is also involved in 2-slit interference, but a particle with rest mass hits the target with the same impact, but does not have 2-slit interference because it is guaranteed to have a rest frame and a co-ordinate ($x-t$) axes in that frame. As a result, it does not require an intrinsic co-ordinate system based on E and p , which regardless of the rest mass number, do depend on rest mass. We argue that ((8)) may be interpreted for momentum as indicating different $x-t$ co-ordinate axes, as:

$$x'/t' = v_1 \text{ or } x'/t'=v_2 \text{ or } x'/t' = v_3 \text{ etc } ((9))$$

As a result, it is not clear which co-ordinate axis applies. Even though there is an intrinsic rest frame for each m_i , each is different. As a result, it may not be too far-fetched to argue that even though the motion of any v value is relative to a rest frame and its co-ordinate axes, an intrinsic co-ordinate scheme based on:

$$\text{Period} = \text{constant}/E \text{ and } \text{wavelength} = \text{constant}/p \quad ((10))$$

fixes a well-defined time and spatial unit or resolution.

This would allow for consistency between the meanings of E and p for both a photon and particle with rest mass. The fact that one is a wave simply means that the period and wavelength may be used to obtain c for the photon, but not for the particle with rest mass. This is already known because it is speed relative to a rest frame which defines motion for a particle with rest mass. The degeneracy of ((8)), however, may be enough to argue momentum is not tied to one particular m_i and v_i , i.e. a unique rest frame. This degeneracy may allow for some freedom in seeking a co-ordinate axes ($x-t$) free definition of a length unit as in the case of the photon and a time unit based on energy.

If that is the case, then a free particle with rest mass still has the sense of a frequency linked with energy which defines a time unit and a wavelength which is linked with momentum and defines a unit in space. Given a rest mass and rest frame, one may have rest frame co-ordinate axes associated with motion:

$$x=vt \quad ((11))$$

but this is motion relative to the rest frame and not an intrinsic $x-t$ scheme based on E and p which have degeneracy features ((8)). We also note that E and p may be measured independently. For example, a strike against a target is based on p and not on E so sets of (E_1,p) and (E_2,p) yield the same target hit. This gives some independence to p and E even though:

$$E = m_0 c^2 / \sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2} \quad \text{and} \quad p = m_0 v / \sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2} \quad ((12))$$

Thus, in terms of interactions, p and E seem to act as independent variables despite ((12)), which does not contradict the association of p with a wavelength and E , a period.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we have used special relativity to link photons with particles with rest mass. We note that one might at first consider these to be completely different objects, but that a Lorentz transformation, derived solely for a particle with rest mass, must contain a velocity constant $b=c$ which is the same in all frames. This might at first be considered only as an upper bound of speed, but we argue that we believe that it has more implications. We argue that a photon has no rest frame and so should not be associated with an $x-t$ co-ordinate axes which implies a rest frame. That is not to say that one cannot use an $x-t$ co-ordinate system to measure x and t for a photon, but this $x-t$ system is based on a ruler and clock at rest. A photon exists outside of the presence of particles with rest mass and so $x=ct$ and $E=pc$ should be the same equation, we argue, leading to: wavelength = constant/ p and period = constant/ E . These two lead directly to the speed c .

A particle with rest mass has a rest frame and its speed relative to this frame which defines motion. Furthermore, E and p are based on m_0 (rest mass) and do not appear to be independent for such a particle as the x and t (for a photon E and p). We argue, however, that a particle with rest mass has measurement independence for E and p . For example, a target hit is based on p and not on E , so $p=m_1v_1=m_2v_2=m_3v_3$ all yield the same result. This degeneracy and independence in an interaction seem to suggest that it may not be far-fetched to associate E and p of a particle with rest mass with a period and wavelength in the same manner as a photon. Even though a rest mass implies a rest frame with a fixed co-ordinate system, $v_1=x'/t'$, $v_2=x'/t'$ etc imply different co-ordinate systems and even the rest frames have different rest masses, m_1 , m_2 etc and so this degeneracy and independence of p from E may be sufficient to allow one to associate wavelength = constant/ p even for a particle with rest mass. This is consistent with the notion that a photon with p and a particle with rest mass with the same p impact a target in the same manner and so should hopefully interact with a 2-slit system in the same way.